

ACCELERATING IMAGE FILTERING PROCESSES ON NVIDIA GRAPHICS PROCESSOR USING CUDA TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: With technological advancements, the volume of data to be processed is rapidly increasing. Image-based data, in particular, require significant computational resources, slowing down processing. This study investigates the efficiency of parallel image filtering on large-scale data using GPU. Filtering was performed in parallel on an NVIDIA graphics processor with CUDA technology, and results were compared to sequential CPU processing. The study shows that GPU-based processing with CUDA significantly outperforms CPU execution, achieving up to ~235 times faster performance for large images. These results confirm the high efficiency of GPU and CUDA technology for image processing.

Keywords: image processing, image filtering, parallel processing, CPU, GPU, CUDA technology

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the rapid growth of data volume, increasing complexity of applications, and rising demands on computing technologies have necessitated the development of new approaches. In particular, the growing diversity of data and the need for rapid processing have significantly increased the demand for efficient and advanced methods in digital information processing technologies. At the same time, the analysis of large-scale data, the development of cloud computing systems, and higher computational requirements have made scientific research in modern computer architectures and algorithmic approaches a pressing issue. The deep integration of information technologies into all sectors has made the performance of computing systems, especially parallel processing capabilities, increasingly important. In many practical applications, saving time is a primary requirement, which drives the development of solutions based on parallel computing methods. Efficient algorithms and architectures are particularly necessary to accelerate computations when processing large-scale digital data [1], [2], [3].

Digital image processing involves a set of algorithmic methods aimed at improving image quality or extracting relevant information. These methods include filtering, segmentation, rasterization, and noise reduction, among others. Such operations often require flexible and efficient hardware capable of processing large amounts of data simultaneously. In these cases, heterogeneous computing systems stand out as universal and high-performance solutions [4], [5]. When processing images or videos, the use of graphics processors (GPUs) is generally more efficient, as they are specifically optimized for such tasks compared to central processing units (CPUs) [6]. The CPU is the main processor of a computer, responsible for executing general-purpose arithmetic, logical, control, and input/output operations. It executes program instructions sequentially and manages overall system performance. In contrast, the GPU is a specialized multi-core processor designed to handle graphics-related computations. Its architecture, based on a large number of parallel cores, makes it particularly effective for processing large volumes of graphical data such as images and videos. The GPU's

hundreds of parallel processing cores enable fast and efficient operations on image and video data, making it a superior tool for handling graphical information in modern computing systems [7]. The following figure illustrates the main architectural differences between CPUs and GPUs (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Data exchange process between CPU and GPU [7].

As observed in the figure above, GPUs possess thousands of cores compared to CPUs. However, GPUs transfer data from the CPU memory to their own memory for processing and operate on this data according to instructions provided by the CPU. As the volume of data loaded into GPU memory increases, a slowdown in GPU processing performance can occur. To mitigate this issue and enhance efficiency, it is advisable to employ parallel processing technologies on the GPU.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The rapid development of digital technologies has led to increasing complexity in tasks related to image processing. In fields such as medicine, industry, security, transportation, and artificial intelligence, the demand for fast and efficient image processing continues to grow. Parallel computing technologies, particularly parallel processing on GPUs, play a crucial role in addressing these challenges. These technologies significantly enhance the efficiency of image processing operations [8].

Image processing. Image processing refers to a set of algorithmic methods aimed at analyzing digital images, improving their quality, extracting relevant information, or adapting them to a required format

[5]. Image processing algorithms perform functions such as modifying or enhancing images and extracting useful information. These technologies are widely applied in artificial intelligence, computer vision, medical image analysis, and satellite image processing. The process of image processing involves applying specific mathematical operations to each pixel of an image [9]. Common image processing techniques include filtering, edge detection, segmentation, and noise reduction (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Main methods of image processing.

Thus, image processing can be considered a type of signal processing, where the input consists of images or videos, and the output is either the processed image or the useful information extracted from it.

Gaussian filter. Gaussian Blur is one of the most widely used filtering algorithms for smoothing images and reducing noise [10]. This algorithm is based on the Gaussian function, where each pixel is assigned a weight coefficient according to its distance from the central pixel. As a result, pixels closer to the center have a stronger influence, while those farther away contribute less. Grayscale and color images often contain noise, brightness variations, or random color fluctuations. These irregularities can cause significant differences between neighboring pixels, leading to a reduction in image quality [11]. The Gaussian Blur algorithm addresses this problem by smoothing the image to suppress noise. The mathematical expression for the Gaussian smoothing filter applied to reduce noise is given by:

$$G_{(x,y)} = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (1)$$

where x and y represent the pixel's distance from the center, and σ determines the intensity of the

smoothing. Larger σ values result in stronger smoothing. The kernel is typically of size 3×3 , 5×5 , or 7×7 ; for example, a commonly used 3×3 kernel is:

$$\frac{1}{16} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 1 \\ 2 & 4 & 2 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

In this matrix, the central element has the highest weight, exerting the greatest influence on the central pixel, while surrounding elements represent the contribution of neighboring pixels. The sum of the weights is usually normalized to 1.

The Gaussian filter effectively reduces random noise by averaging the values of neighboring pixels, thereby smoothing abrupt variations and the overall image. However, object edges may become slightly blurred during filtering, as fine details and sharp lines are also softened. Nevertheless, the Gaussian filter remains one of the most commonly used methods in image processing, particularly in pre-processing stages to enhance image quality before complex analysis or object detection algorithms.

Parallel image processing. In modern computing systems, the speed of processing large-scale data, particularly images and videos, is critical. Traditional sequential processing approaches are often insufficient for such resource-intensive tasks. Consequently, parallel computing technologies have become increasingly important [12]. These technologies distribute tasks across multiple processor cores or independent computing units, enabling simultaneous execution (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Data processing (a-serial processing, b-parallel processing).

Parallel processing offers significant advantages in operations such as image analysis,

smoothing, filtering, segmentation, and classification. Large images can be divided into smaller sections, each processed independently, which reduces overall execution time and increases system efficiency. GPUs and their primary programming model, CUDA (Compute Unified Device Architecture), play a key role in effectively parallelizing these operations. With hundreds or thousands of cores, GPUs can perform large numbers of repetitive computations simultaneously, making them highly efficient for pixel-level image analysis, applying filters, and matrix operations.

CUDA-based parallel image processing. Image processing, especially for high-resolution images and videos, requires substantial computational power. Traditional CPU-based sequential approaches often fail to provide sufficient performance for such tasks [13]. Therefore, implementing image processing on GPUs has become both practical and efficient. NVIDIA’s CUDA technology provides an effective programming model that enables full utilization of GPU cores for parallel image processing [14].

CUDA technology. CUDA is a specialized parallel computing platform developed by NVIDIA, allowing efficient parallel data processing on NVIDIA GPUs [15]. GPUs are widely used to accelerate computation-intensive tasks, including graphics modeling and image/video processing [16]. Many image processing algorithms are inherently parallelizable, making GPU architectures particularly suitable. In heterogeneous computing systems based on GPUs, CUDA is an essential tool for high-performance parallel image processing. The CUDA programming model organizes parallel computation into grids and blocks. A grid is a collection of blocks, and each block contains multiple threads (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Computational model of the CUDA architecture [15].

In this model, the device code runs on the GPU, while the host code runs on the CPU. Each thread executes an independent computation, typically on a single pixel or element. Optimal selection of grid and block sizes is crucial for maximizing efficiency; incorrect sizing may reduce effective GPU resource utilization [17]. All threads and blocks can access global memory, although access speed is slower. Shared memory, available to all threads within a block, provides approximately ten times faster access compared to global memory. Additionally, each thread has local memory for even faster access. Effective use of this memory hierarchy, particularly during preprocessing tasks such as filtering, convolution, or matrix operations, significantly enhances computational speed [18], [19]. Portions of the image can be loaded from global memory into shared memory within a block, allowing fast inter-thread data exchange, reducing global memory accesses, and improving overall performance (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Memory model of the CUDA architecture.

Proper memory management and full utilization of CUDA architecture are essential for achieving real-time performance in image processing applications.

Parallel image processing using CUDA. The CUDA programming model, which extends the C language, enables parallel image processing in heterogeneous computing systems [20]. With this technology, image processing tasks are primarily executed on the GPU, while certain operations remain under CPU control. The CUDA-based image processing workflow typically consists of four stages: (1) the GPU loads data from the main memory into its own memory, (2) the CPU sends the necessary instructions to the GPU, (3) the GPU performs parallel image processing operations, and (4) the processed results are transferred back to main memory (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Structure of the GPU block and stages of image processing [20].

It is not necessary to write the entire image processing program in CUDA. Instead, CUDA is invoked selectively for computationally intensive or critical stages, allowing these tasks to be executed efficiently on the GPU. This approach leverages the GPU for parallel processing while maintaining CPU control over management and routing operations, ensuring an effective heterogeneous computing

workflow for image processing and other parallel tasks.

Research results. In this study, parallel image processing was performed using a Gaussian filter implemented with CUDA technology. The primary focus was on accelerating computation during image processing. GPUs are known to achieve significantly higher computational performance compared to central processing units (CPUs). To evaluate the efficiency of CUDA-based parallel image processing, experiments were conducted under specific technical conditions. Computations were carried out on a system equipped with both GPU and CPU, with the utilized devices, memory sizes, and other technical parameters presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Specifications of the devices used in the study

Model processor	Cores/Thread	Cache memory processor L1 / L2 / L3	Parallel technologies
Intel Core i7-12650H	20/16	684 KB / 9.5 MB / 24 MB	-
Nvidia GeForce RTX 3070	5120	GPU memory (8GB VRAM)	CUDA (12.4 v.)

The study demonstrated the effectiveness of CUDA for image processing tasks. Various image sizes (512×512, 1024×1024, 3200×2400) were processed with the Gaussian filter, and execution times on CPU and GPU were compared. Performance on the GPU was further enhanced using a block-based approach and shared memory. The results indicate that applying the Gaussian filter with CUDA achieves significantly faster processing compared to the CPU. These differences are clearly illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2. Performance results of Gaussian filtering

Input image	CPU (ms)	GPU (ms)	Percent Decrease
512x512	16	0.67	2,288
1024x1024	62	0.84	7,280
3200x2400	688	2.92	23,461

The percent decrease indicates the reduction in processing time when using a GPU compared to a CPU. It can be calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Percent Decrease} = \frac{CPU_{time} - GPU_{time}}{CPU_{time}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where GPU_{time} is the time required for computation on the GPU (typically measured in milliseconds), and CPU_{time} is the time required on the CPU.

In this study, computational efficiency was analyzed by comparing CPU and GPU execution times for Gaussian filter-based image processing. The results show that parallel processing on the GPU using CUDA achieved significantly faster performance compared to the CPU. As illustrated in the table, the efficiency of the GPU increases with larger image sizes. For instance, when processing a 3200×2400 image, GPU execution time was reduced by 23.46% compared to the CPU. This demonstrates that CUDA-based parallel computing provides an effective solution for handling large-scale images.

CONCLUSION

This study compared image processing using a Gaussian filter on both CPU and GPU platforms. The parallel approach implemented on the GPU using CUDA demonstrated a significant speedup over traditional sequential CPU computations. The GPU achieved the following speedup values: approximately 23.88× for 512×512 images, 73.81× for 1024×1024 images, and 235.62× for 3200×2400 images. These results indicate that GPU efficiency increases with larger image sizes. In particular, for large-scale images, GPUs combined with CUDA technology provide near real-time processing with substantially

higher computational performance. In modern heterogeneous computing systems (CPU+GPU), image processing tasks are executed in parallel on the GPU, while sequential operations are handled by the CPU. Using CUDA, the time required for image processing on the GPU is considerably lower than on the CPU, highlighting the clear advantage of GPU acceleration for image processing tasks. Based on the findings of this study, we recommend leveraging NVIDIA GPUs and CUDA technology to perform parallel processing of large-scale data in available computing systems.

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